

Appendix C: X-ray spectra of the X-HESS AGN

In this section we report a complete description of the best-fit spectral results for each AGN in the X-HESS sample. Specifically, the best-fit model and parameters of each observation are listed in Table C.1, while the corresponding X-ray spectrum can be visualised in Fig. C.1, where data from EPIC-pn, MOS1 and MOS2 are shown in black, red and blue, respectively. Solid green line indicates the best-fit model. The bottom panel in each plot describes the ratio between the data points and the best-fit model.

As already stated in § 3.2, we find that the X-ray continuum of the X-HESS sources can be well reproduced by a phenomenological model described by a power law absorbed by the Galactic gas column density plus, in some cases, a blackbody component to account for the soft excess. However, some of the X-HESS AGN are characterised by at least one spectrum that requires relatively more complex models, that we discuss below. In each case, the adoption of an additional model component is favoured whenever the value of ΔW -stat with respect to the corresponding change of degrees of freedom is significant at 95% confidence level for the number of interesting parameters characterising the additional component.

X-HESS 7. This AGN is located at redshift $z \sim 1$ and has been serendipitously observed by *XMM-Newton* for a total of five times between July 2003 and January 2015. Our spectroscopic analysis indicates that the broadband spectrum of SDSS J023410.58–085213.5 can be described by a simple model comprising a power-law continuum modified by Galactic absorption. Moreover, in three spectra we find evidence for cold absorption by a gas cloud with a column density of around $\sim 3 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ which we accounted for with the `zTBabs` component in XSPEC. The power-law continuum is quite hard, with the photon index varying between a minimum of ~ 1.3 and a maximum of ~ 1.6 . According to NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (NED)¹ this source has not been observed yet in the radio (apparently the only case among the X-HESS AGN) and since such low values of Γ are not typically expected for a RQ, type-1 AGN, while more commonly seen in RL sources, we cannot exclude a priori that this AGN actually belongs to the class of radio-loud quasars.

X-HESS 9. The ninth X-HESS AGN is located at redshift $z \sim 0.7$ and has a total of four available observations obtained in the same year, from July to August 2017. In general, a good description of the broadband X-ray spectrum is provided by a model consisting of a power-law continuum modified by Galactic absorption. In one spectrum, however, we find necessary to include a cold absorption component, modelled with `zTBabs` in XSPEC, to take into account a thick, neutral absorber of column width $N_{\text{H}} \sim 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. No evidence of such an absorption structure is found in the other observations. The power-law continuum is characterised by photon indices with values ranging from a minimum of ~ 1.4 to a maximum of ~ 1.7 , and this AGN does not show large variations in both the soft and hard X-ray fluxes over the different observations.

X-HESS 13. This source has three available *XMM-Newton* observations carried out between May 2017 and November 2018, with the first two observations being separated by only one day and thus almost coincident. This AGN is also known as Ton 28 and, specifically, the two 2017 observations were analysed by

Nardini et al. (2019), who found an absorption feature at ~ 6.97 keV that they identified as blueshifted absorption by Fe xxvi associated with a UFO with a velocity of $\sim 0.25 - 0.30 c$. For these two observations we find that a good description of the hard X-ray spectrum is provided by a power law modified by Galactic absorption plus an emission feature at $\sim 6.82 - 6.86$ keV, that Nardini et al. (2019) ascribed to a superposition of fluorescent $K\alpha$ lines from Fe xxv-xxvi, confirming the existence of highly ionised gas in the nuclear regions of Ton 28. In our simplified spectral modelling, even if some negative residuals around 9.2 keV are actually visible, we cannot constrain the UFO absorption feature and including such an absorption component does not provide a better spectral fit in terms of the W-statistic. For this reason we refer the reader to the paper by Nardini et al. (2019) for a detailed spectroscopic analysis of the UFO absorption feature. We find a considerable excess of soft emission when we extend our spectral analysis to the soft X-rays. While in the first observation such soft excess can be well described by a single blackbody component with $kT_{\text{bb}} \sim 126$ eV, we need to include two blackbody components of temperatures ~ 112 and ~ 260 eV to account for the large soft X-ray emission. The photon index Γ undergoes a small variation, moving from a value of ~ 2.3 in the first observation to ~ 2.2 in the second. For the most recent 2018 observation, a good description of the broadband X-ray continuum is provided by a model consisting of a power law of photon index ~ 2.5 modified by Galactic absorption plus a blackbody component of temperature ~ 126 eV to account for the soft excess. We also find that the hard portion of the X-ray spectrum is characterised by the appearance of an emission feature at ~ 6.54 keV that we model with a Gaussian of $EW \sim 340$ eV and is likely ascribable to Fe $K\alpha$ emission from ionised iron. The width of the line is unconstrained, and we fix it to a value consistent with the energy resolution of the instruments of 100 eV. In the 2018 observation we find no trace of the UFO absorption feature that was present in the previous observations.

X-HESS 20. This X-HESS AGN is found at redshift $z \sim 0.1$ and has been observed twice by *XMM-Newton* in June 2001 and January 2016, respectively. This source is a well known NLSy1, frequently referred to as PG 1404+226, that has been extensively studied for its peculiar spectral and emission features (e.g. Dasgupta et al. 2005; Crummy et al. 2005; Mallick & Dewangan 2018, and references therein). Concerning the 2001 *XMM-Newton* observation, the authors found that the broadband X-ray spectrum of PG 1404+226 could be described by a baseline model consisting of a power-law continuum modified by Galactic absorption, plus a blackbody component to account for the unusually strong excess of soft X-ray emission. The results from our spectroscopic analysis agree with their previous findings, and we find a value of $\Gamma \sim 1.74$ and a blackbody temperature of $kT_{\text{bb}} \sim 114$ eV, both consistent within the errors to what reported in e.g. Dasgupta et al. (2005). Moreover, the same authors did also find negative residuals at around 1 and 3 keV, respectively, that were modelled with three Gaussian absorption lines at ~ 1 , ~ 1.17 and ~ 3.07 keV. We also find these residuals, but in our case only the absorption feature at ~ 1 keV provides a significant improvement to the spectral fit, i.e. $\Delta W \sim 33$ for two degrees of freedom. By modelling such an absorption feature with a Gaussian component (`zgauss` in XSPEC), we find that the line centroid is at $E \sim 1.01$ keV, possibly ascribable to absorption by ionised Ne or Fe, with $\sigma \sim 140$ eV and an equivalent width of $EW \sim -90$ eV. Dasgupta et al. (2005) reported on a considerable intra-observation flux variability that we also ob-

¹ <https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu>.

serve in the EPIC light curves, and they also concluded that there might be a connection between the flux and spectral variability, as the absorption features get more pronounced in the high-flux state. The most recent 2016 *XMM-Newton* observation has been analysed in great detail by Mallick & Dewangan (2018), who carried out both a spectral and timing study. They found a large short-term, intra-observation flux variability consisting of an exponential increase of the X-ray (0.3–8 keV) by a factor of ~ 7 in about 10 ks followed by a sharp drop. A baseline model similar to the one adopted by Dasgupta et al. (2005) was used to model the broadband X-ray spectrum of PG 1404+226. In this case, however, the soft X-ray emission below ~ 1 keV was much more complex, probably due to the longer exposure of the 2016 observation, and revealed the presence of a WA, consisting of a highly ionised ($\xi \sim 600 \text{ erg cm s}^{-1}$) Ne x Ly α absorbing cloud along the line of sight with a column density of $N_{\text{H}} \sim 5 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, that the authors accounted for by means of an *ad-hoc* model in XSTAR. For our purposes, a phenomenological description of the broadband X-ray spectrum by means of a power-law continuum modified by Galactic absorption, plus a blackbody component to account for the excess of soft X-ray emission and the `zxipcf` component to deal with the ionised absorption of the WA is sufficient to provide a good spectral fit and we refer the reader to the paper by Mallick & Dewangan (2018) for a more detailed treatment. We find that the photon index has a value of $\Gamma \sim 1.68$ and the blackbody temperature is around $kT_{\text{bb}} \sim 115$ eV, consistent within the 90% confidence level with the values reported by Mallick & Dewangan (2018). The `zxipcf` component indicates the presence of an absorbing gas cloud with a column density of $N_{\text{H}} \sim 36 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and ionisation parameter of $\log(\xi/\text{erg cm s}^{-1}) \sim 3.1$. In addition, we also find negative residuals around ~ 1 keV that we account for by including a Gaussian absorption line, with centroid energy of $E \sim 1.06$ keV, $\sigma \sim 120$ eV and an equivalent width of $EW \sim -80$ eV. Between the two observations the soft X-ray flux has dropped by a factor of ~ 2 , while the hard X-ray emission has maintained approximately the same level.

X-HESS 21. This AGN is a NLSy1 galaxy, also known as PG 1448+273, that has been extensively studied by means of detailed spectral analyses due to the presence of a powerful and variable UFO in its X-ray spectrum (for an indepth discussion, see e.g. Kosec et al. 2020; Laurenti et al. 2021; Reeves et al. 2023). Here it will be sufficient to examine the differences between the phenomenological descriptions of the broadband X-ray spectrum for the two available *XMM-Newton* observations in the X-HESS sample. The 2003 observation was studied by Inoue et al. (2007), who found that the broadband X-ray spectrum of PG 1448+273 was described well by a baseline model consisting of a power-law continuum modified by Galactic absorption, plus two blackbody components two account for the complex excess of soft X-ray emission, a Gaussian emission line at $E \sim 6$ keV to include the Fe K α emission and an edge component to deal with an absorption feature in the soft X-rays. Our independent analysis is in partial agreement with their findings and the best-fit model is approximately the same described by Inoue et al. (2007), expect for the lack of the need to include an edge component in the soft X-ray portion of the spectrum. We find the photon index has a value of $\Gamma \sim 2.27$ and the blackbody temperatures are $kT_{\text{bb}} \sim 80$ eV and $kT_{\text{bb}} \sim 170$ eV, respectively. Including a Gaussian emission line at around 6.4 keV leads to a net improvement of the spectral fit, with a $\Delta W \sim 16$ for two degrees of freedom, but we need to fix the line width to the value

of 200 eV returned by the fit, similarly to the approach by Inoue et al. (2007), otherwise the line energy cannot be resolved. We find the line centroid energy at $E \sim 6.49$ keV with an equivalent width of around $EW \sim 190$ eV. For the most recent 2017 observation, we find that a good description of the broadband X-ray spectrum is provided by a similar model, but in this case a single blackbody component is necessary to account for the soft X-ray emission and an additional Gaussian line is needed to model the UFO absorption feature (Kosec et al. 2020; Laurenti et al. 2021; Reeves et al. 2023). We find that the photon index has a value of $\Gamma \sim 1.9$ and the blackbody temperature is now of $kT_{\text{bb}} \sim 110$ eV. To constrain the emission line we must fix its width to 100 eV, the value returned by the fit, while the absorption line has a width of $\sigma \sim 260$ eV. The line centroid energies are $E \sim 6.65$ keV and $E \sim 7.48$ keV, respectively, and the former has an equivalent width is $EW \sim 100$ eV, while the latter has $EW \sim -340$ eV. The soft X-ray flux has dropped by a factor of ~ 2 between the two observations and the hard X-ray flux has diminished by around $\sim 50\%$ of its original value observed in 2003.

A more recent joint *XMM-Newton* and *NuSTAR* observation of PG 1448+273 was carried out in 2022 and Reeves et al. (2023) discovered that the UFO is persistent, significantly faster than in the previous 2017 observation and rapidly variable on timescales down to 10 ks.

X-HESS 25. This AGN is found at $z \sim 0.7$ and has been observed in July 2012. We find that the broadband X-ray continuum may be described by a simple model comprising a power law with $\Gamma \sim 1.9$ modified by Galactic absorption. Positive residuals emerge below ~ 4 keV and we include a Gaussian line to deal with them. We obtain a significant improvement of the spectral fit by including the line, being $\Delta W \sim 15$ for two degrees of freedom. The line centroid is at $E \sim 3.8$ keV, with a width of $\sigma \sim 190$ eV that we must keep fixed to the best-fit value otherwise it cannot be constrained, and the equivalent width is $EW \sim 270$ eV. This line can be tentatively identified with a contribution from Ca xix emission at ~ 3.9 keV.

X-HESS 30. This AGN is located at $z \sim 0.3$ and has been observed in September 2016. We find that the broadband X-ray continuum may be described by a simple model comprising a power law with $\Gamma \sim 2.3$ modified by Galactic absorption. Negative residuals emerge around ~ 1 keV and we include a Gaussian line to take them into account. The spectral fit improves by including the line, being $\Delta W > 10$ for two degrees of freedom. The line centroid is at $E \sim 1.10$ keV, with an unresolved width, and the equivalent width is $EW \sim -70$ eV. This line can be tentatively ascribed to absorption by Fe xvii and/or Fe xviii.

X-HESS 32. This AGN lies at $z \sim 1.50$ and has been observed in October 2014. We find that the broadband X-ray continuum may be described by a simple model comprising a power law with $\Gamma \sim 1.9$ modified by Galactic absorption. Positive residuals emerge around ~ 6.4 keV and we deal with them by adding a Gaussian line to the baseline model. We obtain a significant improvement of the spectral fit by including the line, being $\Delta W \sim 16$ for two degrees of freedom. The line centroid is at $E \sim 6.58$ keV, the width is unresolved, and the equivalent width is $EW \sim 60$ eV. This line can be tentatively identified with a contribution from Fe K α emission from ionised iron, likely Fe xxv.

X-HESS 37. This X-HESS AGN lies at $z \sim 0.16$ and has been observed by *XMM-Newton* in October 2005. The broadband X-ray continuum may be described by a baseline model consisting of a power law modified by Galactic absorption, plus two blackbody components necessary to account for the excess of soft X-ray emission. The photon index has a value of $\Gamma \sim 2.3$ and the blackbody temperature of the two components is $kT_{\text{bb}} \sim 134$ eV and $kT_{\text{bb}} \sim 70$ eV, respectively. We find positive residuals around ~ 1 keV that we model with a Gaussian line. The fit improvement is significant, i.e. $\Delta W \sim 25$ for three degrees of freedom, by including the emission line in the best-fit model. The line width is $\sigma \sim 100$ eV and the centroid energy is $E \sim 0.94$ keV, with an equivalent width of $EW \sim 50$ eV, and is likely due to emission by ionised iron.

X-HESS 54. This source is an AGN at redshift $z \sim 3.3$ that has been observed by *XMM-Newton* in December 2017. We find that the broadband X-ray spectrum can be described well by a baseline model consisting of a power-law continuum with $\Gamma \sim 1.7$ modified by Galactic absorption. The soft portion of the X-ray spectrum shows clear signatures of absorption that we try to model with different components. The spectral fit has a significant improvement, being $\Delta W \sim 20$ for one degree of freedom, by including absorption by a cold gas cloud (z_{TBabs} in XSPEC). We find that such absorber has a column width of around $N_{\text{H}} \sim 6 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

X-HESS 56. This AGN is at redshift $z \sim 1.6$ and has been observed by *XMM-Newton* in January 2016. We find that a satisfactory description of the broadband X-ray continuum is provided by a baseline model consisting of a power-law with $\Gamma \sim 1.8$ modified by Galactic absorption. The hard portion of the X-ray spectrum is dominated by a broad absorption feature below ~ 10 keV in the rest frame. We obtain a significant improvement of the spectral fit, being $\Delta W \sim 40$ for two degrees of freedom, by including an absorption edge in the best-fit model with z_{edge} in XSPEC, that is likely ascribable to Fe xxvi. The energy of the absorption edge is $E \sim 9.3$ keV with $\tau \sim 1.1$. The presence of this spectral feature may be indicative of resonant absorption lines due to the same ion species, thus potentially suggesting that the absorption edge can represent a broad and blueshifted absorption line likely linked to a UFO. However, if we substitute the edge with a Gaussian line in absorption, this leads to a worsening of the spectral fit and the impossibility to constrain the line energy and width.

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Table C.1: Best fitting spectral parameters for the broadband ($E = 0.3 - 10$ keV) X-ray spectra of the X-HESS AGN, along with derived quantities from EPIC and OM data.

ID	#	Model	(3)	Γ	(5)	kT_{bb}	(6)	$F_{0.5-2\text{keV}}$	(7)	$F_{2-10\text{keV}}$	(8)	$\log L_{0.5-2\text{keV}}$	(9)	$\log L_{2-10\text{keV}}$	(10)	$k_{\text{bol},X}$	(11)	$\log L_{2\text{keV}}$	(12)	$\log L_{2500\text{\AA}}$	(13)	$\log L_{4400\text{\AA}}$	(14)	α_{Ox}	(15)	$\log A_{\text{Edd},\text{O/UV}}$	(16)	$R_{\text{S/p}}$	(17)
1	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.10 (34)	1.9 ± 0.3	100 ± 20	2.6 ^{+0.2} _{-0.6}	3.1 ^{+1.0} _{-0.9}	44.16 ^{+0.08} _{-0.07}	43.80 ± 0.08	60 ± 30	25.88 ^{+0.06} _{-0.07}	29.62 ± 0.02	29.65 ± 0.02	-1.44 ^{+0.02} _{-0.03}	-0.4	2.2 ± 2.1													
1	2	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.05 (95)	2.2 ± 0.1	130 ± 10	3.9 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	2.5 ± 0.3	44.26 ± 0.02	43.78 ± 0.04	70 ± 30	25.98 ± 0.03	29.86 ± 0.01	29.89 ± 0.01	-1.49 ± 0.01	-0.1	1.4 ± 0.4													
1	3	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.00 (108)	2.1 ± 0.1	110 ± 10	3.6 ^{+0.3} _{-0.1}	3.1 ± 0.5	44.23 ± 0.03	43.86 ± 0.04	60 ± 30	26.01 ± 0.03	29.92 ± 0.02	29.95 ± 0.02	-1.50 ± 0.01	-0.1	1.2 ± 0.4													
1	4	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.00 (98)	2.49 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}	108 ± 9	7.1 ^{+0.2} _{-0.3}	3.7 ± 0.4	44.53 ± 0.02	44.03 ± 0.03	40 ± 20	26.30 ± 0.02	29.93 ± 0.01	29.96 ± 0.01	-1.39 ± 0.01	0.0	0.7 ± 0.2													
1	5	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.91 (63)	2.4 ± 0.1	120 ± 10	4.0 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	2.0 ± 0.3	44.28 ± 0.02	43.76 ± 0.03	70 ± 30	26.02 ± 0.03	29.85 ± 0.01	29.88 ± 0.01	-1.47 ± 0.01	-0.1	1.0 ± 0.3													
1	6	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.88 (95)	2.6 ± 0.2	140 ± 20	5.0 ± 0.2	2.1 ± 0.3	44.32 ± 0.02	43.80 ± 0.04	60 ± 30	26.11 ± 0.03	29.89 ± 0.02	29.92 ± 0.02	-1.45 ± 0.01	-0.1	0.6 ± 0.2													
1	7	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.97 (93)	2.3 ± 0.2	140 ± 10	5.1 ^{+0.2} _{-0.3}	2.9 ± 0.4	44.36 ± 0.02	43.89 ± 0.04	50 ± 20	26.11 ± 0.03	29.88 ± 0.01	29.91 ± 0.01	-1.45 ± 0.01	-0.1	1.2 ± 0.4													
1	8	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.99 (48)	1.9 ± 0.3	110 ± 20	2.7 ^{+0.1} _{-0.5}	3.0 ^{+1.0} _{-0.2}	44.20 ^{+0.07} _{-0.06}	43.8 ± 0.1	60 ± 30	25.84 ^{+0.07} _{-0.08}	29.84 ± 0.01	29.87 ± 0.01	-1.54 ± 0.03	-0.1	2.6 ± 2.3													
1	9	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.06 (134)	2.40 ± 0.09	140 ± 10	8.0 ± 0.2	4.5 ± 0.4	44.51 ± 0.01	44.09 ± 0.02	30 ± 20	26.33 ± 0.02	29.80 ± 0.03	30.03 ± 0.04	-1.33 ± 0.01	0.0	0.7 ± 0.1													
1	10	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.99 (114)	2.20 ± 0.09	140 ± 10	4.4 ± 0.1	3.3 ± 0.3	44.18 ± 0.02	43.90 ± 0.02	50 ± 20	26.09 ± 0.02	29.89 ± 0.03	30.00 ± 0.04	-1.46 ± 0.01	0.0	0.6 ± 0.1													
1	11	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.96 (95)	2.6 ± 0.1	130 ± 10	6.8 ± 0.2	2.9 ± 0.3	44.50 ± 0.02	43.94 ± 0.03	50 ± 20	26.24 ± 0.02	29.84 ± 0.03	29.84 ± 0.03	-1.38 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.7 ± 0.2													
1	12	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.99 (86)	2.40 ± 0.09	100 ± 20	3.3 ^{+0.02} _{-0.17}	2.2 ± 0.2	44.13 ^{+0.04} _{-0.03}	43.77 ± 0.03	70 ± 30	26.01 ± 0.02	29.93 ± 0.02	30.06 ± 0.03	-1.50 ± 0.01	0.1	0.5 ± 0.2													
1	13	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.99 (61)	2.0 ± 0.1	120 ± 10	2.19 ^{+0.07} _{-0.12}	2.3 ± 0.3	43.94 ± 0.03	43.69 ± 0.03	80 ± 40	25.79 ± 0.03	29.86 ± 0.02	30.21 ± 0.02	-1.56 ± 0.01	0.2	1.2 ± 0.3													
1	14	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.91 (91)	2.37 ± 0.08	118 ± 7	4.04 ^{+0.09} _{-0.12}	2.4 ± 0.2	44.28 ± 0.01	43.81 ± 0.02	60 ± 30	26.04 ± 0.02	29.81 ± 0.03	30.20 ± 0.02	-1.45 ± 0.01	0.2	1.0 ± 0.1													
1	15	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.05 (132)	2.43 ± 0.08	130 ± 10	5.16 ^{+0.09} _{-0.12}	2.8 ± 0.2	44.34 ± 0.01	43.90 ± 0.02	50 ± 20	26.15 ± 0.02	29.89 ± 0.02	29.90 ± 0.02	-1.44 ± 0.01	-0.1	0.7 ± 0.1													
2	1	const*TBabs*zpo	0.96 (78)	2.1 ± 0.1	-	9.3 ± 0.6	1.1 ± 1	45.07 ± 0.05	45.06 ± 0.03	110 ± 50	27.21 ± 0.03	31.37 ± 0.01	31.40 ± 0.01	-1.60 ± 0.01	-0.2	-													
2	2	const*TBabs*zpo	0.91 (115)	2.33 ± 0.07	-	9.2 ± 0.3	7.7 ± 0.7	45.15 ± 0.03	45.00 ± 0.02	120 ± 60	27.22 ± 0.02	31.36 ± 0.01	31.39 ± 0.01	-1.59 ± 0.01	-0.2	-													
2	3	const*TBabs*zpo	1.01 (174)	2.06 ± 0.02	-	8.4 ± 0.1	10.5 ± 0.3	45.01 ± 0.01	45.04 ± 0.01	110 ± 50	27.16 ± 0.01	31.30 ± 0.01	31.33 ± 0.01	-1.59 ± 0.01	-0.3	-													
2	4	const*TBabs*zpo	1.01 (43)	2.2 ± 0.2	-	7.9 ^{+0.8} _{-0.9}	8 ⁺³ ₋₃	45.04 ± 0.09	44.97 ± 0.06	130 ± 60	27.15 ± 0.05	-	-	-	-	-													
2	5	const*TBabs*zpo	0.82 (37)	2.3 ± 0.2	-	13 ± 1	11 ⁺² ₋₂	45.29 ± 0.08	45.15 ± 0.06	90 ± 40	27.36 ± 0.04	31.41 ± 0.01	31.44 ± 0.01	-1.55 ± 0.02	-0.2	-													
2	6	const*TBabs*zpo	1.02 (52)	1.77 ± 0.08	-	7.8 ± 0.4	15 ± 2	44.86 ± 0.04	45.07 ± 0.03	100 ± 50	27.10 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-													
2	7	const*TBabs*zpo	0.94 (43)	1.45 ± 0.08	-	5.1 ± 0.3	15 ± 2	44.55 ± 0.04	44.98 ± 0.02	130 ± 60	26.88 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-													
2	8	const*TBabs*zpo	0.98 (121)	1.87 ± 0.08	-	6.3 ± 0.3	10 ± 1	44.81 ± 0.04	44.96 ± 0.03	130 ± 60	27.02 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-													
2	9	const*TBabs*zpo	1.00 (66)	1.77 ± 0.07	-	8.1 ± 0.3	15 ± 1	44.88 ± 0.04	45.09 ± 0.02	100 ± 50	27.12 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-													
2	10	const*TBabs*zpo	0.94 (56)	1.7 ± 0.1	-	4.9 ± 0.3	10 ± 1	44.66 ± 0.05	44.91 ± 0.03	150 ± 70	26.91 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-													
2	11	const*TBabs*zpo	1.15 (40)	1.7 ± 0.1	-	3.9 ^{+0.3} _{-0.5}	8 ⁺¹ ₋₂	44.53 ± 0.08	44.80 ± 0.04	190 ± 90	26.79 ± 0.05	-	-	-	-	-													
2	12	const*TBabs*zpo	0.90 (95)	1.78 ± 0.09	-	6.0 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	11 ± 1	44.75 ± 0.05	44.96 ± 0.03	130 ± 60	26.99 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-													
2	13	const*TBabs*zpo	1.02 (53)	1.7 ± 0.1	-	5.6 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	11 ± 2	44.70 ± 0.07	44.95 ± 0.04	140 ± 60	26.96 ± 0.04	-	-	-	-	-													
3	1	const*TBabs*zpo	0.92 (25)	1.8 ± 0.3	-	0.8 ± 0.1	1.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4}	43.7 ± 0.1	43.9 ± 0.1	60 ± 30	25.93 ± 0.07	30.01 ± 0.03	30.03 ± 0.03	-1.57 ± 0.03	-0.2	-													
3	2	const*TBabs*zpo	0.97 (82)	2.20 ± 0.07	-	1.30 ± 0.05	1.2 ± 0.1	44.06 ± 0.03	44.00 ± 0.03	50 ± 20	26.17 ± 0.02	30.16 ± 0.04	30.19 ± 0.04	-1.53 ± 0.02	0.0	-													
3	3	const*TBabs*zpo	1.03 (6)	2.2 ^{+0.4} _{-0.3}	-	0.9 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.3	43.9 ± 0.2	43.8 ± 0.1	70 ± 40	25.99 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	-	-	-	-	-													
3	4	const*TBabs*zpo	1.20 (4)	2.0 ± 0.5	-	0.9 ^{+0.2} _{-0.1}	1.1 ^{+0.8} _{-0.9}	43.8 ± 0.2	43.9 ± 0.2	60 ± 40	26.0 ± 0.1	-	-	-	-	-													
3	5	const*TBabs*zpo	1.14 (36)	1.4 ± 0.1	-	0.55 ^{+0.04} _{-0.06}	1.7 ± 0.3	43.41 ^{+0.06} _{-0.05}	43.88 ^{+0.04} _{-0.05}	60 ± 30	25.75 ± 0.04	-	-	-	-	-													
3	6	const*TBabs*zpo	0.96 (7)	1.6 ± 0.2	-	0.51 ^{+0.05} _{-0.07}	1.1 ± 0.3	43.5 ± 0.1	43.77 ± 0.07	80 ± 40	25.73 ± 0.06	-	-	-	-	-													
3	7	const*TBabs*zpo	1.03 (10)	1.7 ± 0.4	-	0.50 ^{+0.09} _{-0.20}	1.0 ^{+0.3} _{-0.7}	43.5 ± 0.2	43.7 ± 0.1	90 ± 50	25.7 ± 0.1	-	-	-	-	-													
3	8	const*TBabs*zpo	0.84 (4)	1.7 ± 0.4	-	0.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.3}	1.3 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	43.6 ± 0.2	43.86 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}	60 ± 30	25.8 ± 0.1	-	-	-	-	-													
4	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.96 (72)	2.1 ± 0.2	130 ⁺²⁰ ₋₃₀	4.6 ^{+0.2} _{-0.3}	3.8 ± 0.6	44.20 ± 0.03	43.92 ± 0.04	100 ± 50	26.07 ± 0.04	30.01 ± 0.01	30.04 ± 0.01	-1.51 ± 0.02	-0.2	0.9 ± 0.4													
4	2	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.10 (104)	2.5 ± 0.1	130 ± 20	7.7 ^{+0.2} _{-0.3}	4.0 ± 0.5	44.44 ± 0.02	44.02 ± 0.03	80 ± 40	26.28 ± 0.03	30.07 ± 0.01	30.10 ± 0.01	-1.45 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.6 ± 0.2													
4	3	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.97 (124)	2.58 ± 0.08	110 ± 20	14.4 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	6.7 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	44.74 ± 0.02	44.27 ± 0.02	50 ± 20	26.57 ± 0.02	30.05 ± 0.01	30.11 ± 0.03	-1.34 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.5 ± 0.1													
4	4	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.93 (141)	2.31 ± 0.07	140 ± 20	19.6 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	13.1 ± 0.9	44.77 ± 0.01	44.50 ± 0.02	30 ± 10	26.71 ± 0.02	30.06 ± 0.01	30.13 ± 0.03	-1.29 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.4 ± 0.1													
4	5	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.95 (130)	2.29 ± 0.08	160 ⁺²⁰ ₋₃₀	5.3 ± 0.1	3.7 ± 0.2	44.18 ± 0.01	43.95 ± 0.02	100 ± 40	26.16 ± 0.02	29.98 ± 0.01	30.01 ± 0.01	-1.47 ± 0.01	-0.3	0.26 ± 0.08													
4	6	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.94 (84)	2.4 ± 0.1	160 ± 30	4.8 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	2.7 ± 0.3	44.17 ± 0.02	43.83 ± 0.03	130 ± 60	26.09 ± 0.02	29.90 ± 0.01	29.93 ± 0.01	-1.46 ± 0.01	-0.4	0.4 ± 0.2													
4	7	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.00 (84)	2.2 ± 0.2	160 ± 30	4.5 ^{+0.2} _{-0.3}	3.2 ± 0.6	44.14 ± 0.03	43.87 ± 0.05	110 ± 50	26.06 ± 0.04	29.94 ± 0.01	29.97 ± 0.01	-1.49 ± 0.02	-0.3	0.6 ± 0.4													

ID # (1) (2)	Model (3)	W-stat/dof (dof) (4)	Γ (5)	kT_{bb} (6)	$F_{2-10\text{keV}}$ (7)	$F_{2-10\text{keV}}$ (8)	$\log L_{0.5-2\text{keV}}$ (9)	$\log L_{2-10\text{keV}}$ (10)	$k_{\text{bol},X}$ (11)	$\log L_{2\text{keV}}$ (12)	$\log L_{2500\text{\AA}}$ (13)	$\log L_{4400\text{\AA}}$ (14)	α_{ox} (15)	$\log A_{\text{Edd},\text{O/UV}}$ (16)	R_{S}/p (17)
5 1	const*TBabs*zpo	0.96 (19)	1.9 ± 0.1	-	2.7 ± 0.2	3.8 ± 0.6	44.81 ± 0.07	44.94 ± 0.03	200 ± 100	27.01 ± 0.04	31.58 ± 0.02	31.61 ± 0.02	-2.14 ± 0.02	-0.3	-
5 2	const*TBabs*zpo	1.14 (38)	1.7 ± 0.1	-	1.2 ± 0.1	2.3 ± 0.4	44.34 ± 0.08	44.62 ± 0.04	500 ± 200	26.61 ± 0.05	31.50 ± 0.02	31.52 ± 0.02	-1.88 ± 0.02	-0.4	-
5 3	const*TBabs*zpo	1.10 (6)	1.4 ± 0.2	-	0.42 ^{+0.04} _{-0.09}	1.2 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	43.8 ± 0.1	44.22 ^{+0.06} _{-0.07}	1200 ± 600	26.12 ± 0.09	31.51 ± 0.03	31.53 ± 0.03	-2.07 ± 0.04	-0.4	-
5 4	const*TBabs*zpo	0.85 (30)	1.7 ± 0.1	-	1.3 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.5	44.40 ± 0.07	44.67 ± 0.04	400 ± 200	26.67 ± 0.05	31.49 ± 0.03	31.51 ± 0.03	-1.85 ± 0.02	-0.4	-
5 5	const*TBabs*zpo	0.97 (49)	2.19 ± 0.07	-	5.2 ± 0.2	4.7 ± 0.5	45.23 ± 0.04	45.18 ± 0.02	130 ± 60	27.35 ± 0.02	31.73 ± 0.01	31.76 ± 0.01	-1.68 ± 0.01	-0.1	-
5 6	const*TBabs*zpo	0.91 (69)	2.28 ± 0.09	-	6.1 ± 0.2	4.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.3}	45.35 ± 0.02	45.23 ± 0.01	120 ± 50	27.44 ± 0.01	31.72 ± 0.01	31.75 ± 0.01	-1.64 ± 0.01	-0.1	-
5 7	const*TBabs*zpo	1.10 (31)	1.7 ± 0.1	-	1.4 ± 0.1	2.9 ± 0.6	44.42 ± 0.07	44.71 ± 0.04	400 ± 200	26.70 ± 0.05	31.71 ± 0.01	31.74 ± 0.01	-1.92 ± 0.02	-0.2	-
6 1	const*TBabs*zpo	1.03 (28)	1.9 ± 0.2	-	7.0 ^{+0.9} _{-1.0}	10 ± 3	43.24 ± 0.07	43.4 ± 0.1	20 ± 10	25.44 ± 0.05	29.53 ± 0.04	29.56 ± 0.04	-1.57 ± 0.02	0.3	-
6 2	const*TBabs*zpo	0.93 (32)	1.8 ± 0.2	-	5.0 ± 0.6	8 ⁺³ ₋₂	43.09 ± 0.06	43.3 ± 0.1	30 ± 10	25.31 ± 0.05	29.44 ± 0.04	29.47 ± 0.04	-1.59 ± 0.02	0.2	-
6 3	const*TBabs*zpo	0.87 (17)	1.7 ± 0.3	-	8 ± 1	17 ⁺⁶ ₋₅	43.3 ± 0.1	43.6 ± 0.1	13 ± 7	25.54 ± 0.06	29.08 ± 0.07	29.11 ± 0.07	-1.36 ± 0.04	-0.2	-
6 4	const*TBabs*zpo	1.01 (24)	1.8 ± 0.2	-	22 ± 2	35 ⁺⁸ ₋₈	43.72 ± 0.05	43.9 ± 0.1	7 ± 3	25.95 ± 0.05	29.79 ± 0.08	29.82 ± 0.08	-1.47 ± 0.04	0.5	-
6 5	const*TBabs*zpo	0.91 (36)	1.8 ± 0.1	-	14 ± 1	25 ⁺⁶ ₋₅	43.54 ± 0.04	43.76 ± 0.08	9 ± 5	25.78 ± 0.04	-	-	-	-	-
6 6	const*TBabs*zpo	1.07 (51)	1.99 ± 0.03	-	22.6 ± 0.4	28 ± 1	43.76 ± 0.01	43.83 ± 0.02	8 ± 4	25.94 ± 0.01	29.89 ± 0.01	29.92 ± 0.01	-1.52 ± 0.01	0.6	-
6 7	const*TBabs*zpo	0.99 (67)	1.54 ± 0.08	-	6.7 ± 0.4	17 ± 2	44.43 ± 0.05	44.80 ± 0.03	1.9 ± 0.9	26.73 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-
7 1	const*TBabs*zTBabs ^(a) *zpo	1.09 (65)	1.6 ± 0.1	-	3.4 ± 0.2	8 ± 1	44.21 ± 0.08	44.51 ± 0.03	4 ± 2	26.39 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-
7 2	const*TBabs*zTBabs ^(a) *zpo	0.92 (85)	1.34 ± 0.08	-	3.2 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	11.3 ± 0.9	44.07 ± 0.05	44.57 ± 0.02	3 ± 1	26.39 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
7 3	const*TBabs*zTBabs ^(b) *zpo	1.02 (109)	1.44 ± 0.05	-	3.5 ± 0.1	10.1 ± 0.6	44.11 ± 0.02	44.54 ± 0.02	3 ± 2	26.44 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
7 4	const*TBabs*zpo	1.03 (108)	1.63 ± 0.07	-	4.4 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	10.8 ± 0.7	44.32 ± 0.04	44.63 ± 0.02	3 ± 1	26.52 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
7 5	const*TBabs*zTBabs ^(c) *zpo	1.03 (179)	1.87 ± 0.04	-	13.0 ± 0.4	20 ± 1	44.43 ± 0.02	44.58 ± 0.02	4 ± 2	26.65 ± 0.01	30.4 ± 0.1	30.4 ± 0.1	-1.44 ± 0.04	0.7	-
8 1	const*TBabs*zpo	1.02 (54)	1.8 ± 0.1	-	8.7 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	16 ± 1	44.24 ± 0.04	44.45 ± 0.04	5 ± 2	26.48 ± 0.03	29.83 ± 0.02	29.86 ± 0.02	-1.29 ± 0.01	0.1	-
8 2	const*TBabs*zpo	1.03 (97)	1.58 ± 0.05	-	5.1 ± 0.2	12.3 ± 0.8	43.96 ± 0.02	44.30 ± 0.02	7 ± 3	26.26 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
8 3	const*TBabs*zpo	0.93 (87)	1.65 ± 0.05	-	5.7 ± 0.2	12.4 ± 0.9	44.03 ± 0.02	44.32 ± 0.02	6 ± 3	26.30 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
8 4	const*TBabs*zpo	0.94 (53)	1.40 ± 0.07	-	1.24 ± 0.06	3.8 ± 0.4	43.35 ± 0.03	43.81 ± 0.03	17 ± 8	25.69 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
9 1	const*TBabs*zpo	0.97 (39)	1.5 ± 0.1	-	1.4 ± 0.1	3.6 ^{+0.8} _{-0.7}	43.42 ± 0.06	43.81 ^{+0.06} _{-0.07}	17 ± 8	25.74 ± 0.04	-	-	-	-	-
9 2	const*TBabs*zpo	1.00 (18)	1.7 ± 0.4	-	1.19 ^{+0.07} _{-0.39}	4.3 ^{+0.6} _{-1.7}	43.6 ± 0.2	43.93 ± 0.06	13 ± 6	25.9 ± 0.1	-	-	-	-	-
9 3	const*TBabs*zTBabs ^(d) *zpo	1.01 (14)	1.6 ± 0.3	-	1.3 ^{+0.2} _{-0.3}	3 ± 1	43.4 ± 0.1	43.8 ± 0.1	17 ± 9	25.72 ± 0.08	-	-	-	-	-
9 4	const*TBabs*zpo	0.88 (31)	1.88 ± 0.07	-	2.13 ± 0.09	3.2 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	43.58 ± 0.03	43.72 ± 0.04	15 ± 7	25.79 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
10 1	const*TBabs*zpo	1.04 (44)	1.7 ± 0.1	-	2.4 ± 0.2	4.6 ^{+0.9} _{-0.9}	43.58 ± 0.05	43.84 ± 0.07	11 ± 5	25.84 ± 0.04	-	-	-	-	-
10 2	const*TBabs*zpo	1.06 (34)	1.9 ± 0.2	-	1.7 ± 0.2	2.6 ^{+0.9} _{-0.7}	43.47 ± 0.06	43.63 ± 0.09	18 ± 9	25.69 ± 0.05	-	-	-	-	-
10 3	const*TBabs*zpo	1.12 (51)	1.6 ± 0.1	-	2.2 ± 0.2	4.8 ^{+1.0} _{-0.9}	43.52 ± 0.05	43.84 ± 0.06	11 ± 5	25.81 ± 0.04	-	-	-	-	-
10 4	const*TBabs*zpo	1.01 (150)	2.6 ± 0.1	-	37 ± 1	17 ± 2	44.45 ± 0.01	44.06 ± 0.03	190 ± 90	26.36 ± 0.02	30.63 ± 0.01	30.66 ± 0.01	-1.64 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.22 ± 0.18
11 1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.94 (196)	2.31 ± 0.08	-	52 ± 1	32 ± 2	44.59 ± 0.01	44.30 ± 0.02	110 ± 50	26.52 ± 0.02	30.62 ± 0.01	30.65 ± 0.01	-1.57 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.4 ± 0.1
11 2	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.06 (202)	2.51 ± 0.07	-	51.2 ^{+0.9} _{-1.0}	27 ± 2	44.61 ± 0.01	44.25 ± 0.02	130 ± 60	26.53 ± 0.01	30.63 ± 0.01	30.66 ± 0.01	-1.57 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.24 ± 0.07
11 3	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.90 (114)	2.46 ± 0.09	-	54 ± 1	30 ± 2	44.62 ± 0.01	44.29 ± 0.03	110 ± 50	26.55 ± 0.02	30.63 ± 0.01	30.66 ± 0.01	-1.57 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.2 ± 0.1
12 1	const*TBabs*zpo	0.89 (19)	1.7 ± 0.3	-	5.9 ^{+0.7} _{-1.5}	11 ± 5	45.1 ± 0.2	45.38 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}	110 ± 50	27.4 ± 0.1	-	-	-	-	-
12 2	const*TBabs*zpo	0.89 (65)	1.77 ± 0.08	-	10.6 ± 0.5	18 ± 2	45.41 ± 0.05	45.63 ± 0.02	60 ± 30	27.65 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-
12 3	const*TBabs*zpo	1.05 (60)	1.56 ± 0.06	-	7.6 ± 0.3	18 ⁺¹ ₋₂	45.16 ± 0.04	45.51 ± 0.02	80 ± 40	27.46 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
12 4	const*TBabs*zpo	1.18 (95)	1.82 ± 0.05	-	7.7 ± 0.2	12.3 ± 0.9	45.29 ± 0.03	45.48 ± 0.01	90 ± 40	27.52 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
13 1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zga ^(e) + zpo)	1.08 (239)	2.28 ± 0.03	-	90.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	54 ± 1	44.65 ± 0.01	44.31 ± 0.01	130 ± 60	26.51 ± 0.01	30.67 ± 0.01	30.73 ± 0.01	-1.60 ± 0.01	0.0	0.71 ± 0.06
13 2	const*TBabs*(zbb + zbb ^(f) + zga ^(g) + zpo)	1.43 (374)	2.18 ± 0.07	-	83.5 ^{+0.3} _{-0.7}	50 ± 1	44.62 ± 0.01	44.28 ± 0.01	130 ± 60	26.49 ± 0.01	30.66 ± 0.01	30.74 ± 0.01	-1.60 ± 0.01	0.0	1.1 ± 0.2
13 3	const*TBabs*(zbb + zga ^(h) + zpo)	1.09 (219)	2.52 ± 0.05	-	131 ± 1	56 ± 2	44.83 ± 0.01	44.36 ± 0.01	110 ± 50	26.63 ± 0.01	30.62 ± 0.01	30.65 ± 0.01	-1.53 ± 0.01	-0.1	0.6 ± 0.1
14 1	const*TBabs*zpo	1.01 (118)	1.90 ± 0.06	-	3.7 ± 0.1	5.4 ± 0.5	44.00 ± 0.02	44.12 ± 0.03	20 ± 10	26.20 ± 0.01	-	-	-	-	-
14 2	const*TBabs*zpo	1.05 (157)	1.87 ± 0.04	-	5.2 ± 0.1	7.9 ± 0.5	44.13 ± 0.02	44.28 ± 0.02	17 ± 8	26.35 ± 0.01	-	-	-	-	-
14 3	const*TBabs*zpo	0.99 (32)	1.9 ± 0.1	-	9.0 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	13 ± 3	44.38 ± 0.05	44.52 ± 0.06	10 ± 5	26.58 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-

ID (1) (2)	Model (3)	W-stat/dof (dof) (4)	Γ (5)	KT_{bb} (6)	$F_{0.5-2\text{keV}}$ (7)	$F_{2-10\text{keV}}$ (8)	$\log L_{0.5-2\text{keV}}$ (9)	$\log L_{2-10\text{keV}}$ (10)	$k_{\text{bol},X}$ (11)	$\log L_{2\text{keV}}$ (12)	$\log L_{2500\text{\AA}}$ (13)	$\log L_{4400\text{\AA}}$ (14)	α_{Ox} (15)	$\log \lambda_{\text{Edd},\text{O/UV}}$ (16)	R_{S}/r (17)
15	1	const*TBabs*zpo	2.52 ± 0.08	-	1.27 ± 0.05	0.76 ^{+0.10} _{-0.08}	44.16 ± 0.03	43.89 ± 0.03	60 ± 30	26.17 ± 0.02	29.87 ± 0.08	29.89 ± 0.08	-1.42 ± 0.03	0.0	-
15	2	const*TBabs*zpo	2.14 ± 0.07	-	1.03 ± 0.04	1.1 ± 0.1	43.94 ± 0.03	43.91 ± 0.03	60 ± 30	26.07 ± 0.02	29.90 ± 0.09	29.9 ± 0.1	-1.47 ± 0.04	0.0	-
16	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.76 ± 0.09	116 ± 7	10.1 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 1	43.61 ± 0.02	43.57 ± 0.03	60 ± 30	25.56 ± 0.02	29.63 ± 0.04	-	-1.56 ± 0.02	-0.3	0.8 ± 0.2
16	2	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.3 ± 0.2	110 ± 10	2.2 ^{+0.1} _{-0.4}	5 ± 1	42.99 ± 0.04	43.12 ± 0.09	170 ± 90	24.94 ± 0.07	29.67 ± 0.02	29.66 ± 0.04	-1.82 ± 0.03	-0.2	1.7 ± 1.0
17	1	const*TBabs*zpo	2.02 ± 0.07	-	2.9 ± 0.2	3.7 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4}	44.77 ± 0.04	44.82 ± 0.03	40 ± 20	26.93 ± 0.03	-	29.74 ± 0.01	-	-	-
17	2	const*TBabs*zpo	2.0 ± 0.1	-	2.9 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	3.9 ± 0.6	44.76 ± 0.06	44.83 ± 0.03	40 ± 20	26.94 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-
18	1	const*TBabs*zpo	2.16 ± 0.06	-	5.6 ± 0.2	5.3 ± 0.5	45.11 ± 0.03	45.07 ± 0.02	30 ± 10	27.23 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
18	2	const*TBabs*zpo	2.08 ± 0.06	-	5.2 ± 0.2	5.6 ± 0.6	45.03 ± 0.03	45.05 ± 0.02	30 ± 10	27.18 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
19	1	const*TBabs*zpo	1.83 ± 0.09	-	8.4 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	13 ± 2	45.22 ± 0.05	45.39 ± 0.03	70 ± 30	27.44 ± 0.03	31.71 ± 0.01	-	-1.64 ± 0.01	0.3	-
19	2	const*TBabs*zpo	2.1 ± 0.1	-	10.3 ± 0.6	10.0 ± 1.5	45.45 ^{+0.05} _{-0.06}	45.42 ± 0.03	60 ± 30	27.58 ± 0.03	31.74 ± 0.01	31.74 ± 0.01	-1.60 ± 0.01	0.3	-
20	1	const*TBabs*(zga ^(l) + zbb + zpo)	1.7 ± 0.1	115 ⁺³ ₋₂	47.9 ± 0.6	17 ± 1	43.18 ± 0.01	42.60 ± 0.03	300 ± 200	24.62 ± 0.03	-	31.77 ± 0.01	-	-	8 ± 2
20	2	const*TBabs*zxipcf ^(l) *(zga ^(l) + zbb + zpo)	1.68 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	115 ± 3	25.3 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	14.7 ^{+0.6} _{-1.0}	42.97 ^{+0.03} _{-0.02}	42.62 ^{+0.05} _{-0.04}	300 ± 100	24.67 ± 0.06	29.36 ± 0.01	-	-1.80 ± 0.02	-0.3	8 ± 6
21	1	const*TBabs*(zga ^(l) + zbb + zpo)	2.27 ± 0.03	173 ⁺⁷ ₋₆	398 ⁺² ₋₁	209 ± 3	43.67 ± 0.01	43.33 ± 0.01	80 ± 40	25.54 ± 0.01	29.09 ± 0.01	29.39 ± 0.01	-1.36 ± 0.01	-0.4	0.71 ± 0.06
21	2	const*TBabs*(zga ^(l) + zga ^(r) + zbb + zpo)	1.89 ± 0.01	110.8 ± 0.3	187.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4}	137 ± 1	43.37 ± 0.01	43.14 ± 0.01	130 ± 60	25.22 ± 0.01	29.08 ± 0.01	29.28 ± 0.01	-1.48 ± 0.01	-0.6	1.3 ± 0.1
22	1	const*TBabs*zpo	1.88 ± 0.05	-	23.6 ± 0.8	36 ⁺³ ₋₂	44.40 ± 0.02	44.54 ± 0.03	2 ± 1	26.61 ± 0.01	-	29.11 ± 0.01	-	-	-
22	2	const*TBabs*zpo	1.7 ± 0.1	-	24 ± 2	46 ± 7	44.38 ^{+0.04} _{-0.05}	44.62 ± 0.05	2 ± 1	26.64 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	-
23	1	const*TBabs*zpo	2.00 ± 0.08	-	2.1 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.3	44.74 ± 0.04	44.81 ^{+0.02} _{-0.03}	80 ± 40	26.92 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
24	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.28 ± 0.09	140 ± 10	14.7 ± 0.3	9.7 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	44.05 ± 0.01	43.77 ± 0.02	30 ± 10	25.97 ± 0.02	29.61 ± 0.03	-	-1.40 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.4 ± 0.1
25	1	const*TBabs*(zpo + zga ^(l))	1.94 ± 0.07	-	2.8 ± 0.1	4.3 ± 0.4	43.87 ± 0.03	44.00 ± 0.03	30 ± 20	26.06 ± 0.02	29.64 ± 0.04	29.64 ± 0.03	-1.37 ± 0.02	-0.5	-
26	1	const*TBabs*zpo	2.14 ± 0.04	-	7.8 ± 0.2	7.8 ± 0.5	45.31 ± 0.02	45.29 ± 0.01	80 ± 40	27.44 ± 0.01	31.44 ± 0.01	29.67 ± 0.04	-1.54 ± 0.01	0.0	-
27	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.4 ± 0.1	130 ± 30	7.0 ^{+0.2} _{-0.4}	4.7 ± 0.6	44.70 ^{+0.04} _{-0.03}	44.36 ± 0.02	80 ± 40	26.59 ± 0.02	30.73 ± 0.02	31.47 ± 0.01	-1.59 ± 0.01	0.1	0.5 ± 0.2
28	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.1 ± 0.1	140 ± 10	14.8 ± 0.5	12 ± 2	44.20 ± 0.01	43.97 ± 0.04	60 ± 30	26.11 ^{+0.02} _{-0.03}	-	30.75 ± 0.02	-	-	0.8 ± 0.3
29	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.1 ± 0.1	160 ± 10	34.0 ^{+0.8} _{-0.9}	26 ± 3	44.61 ± 0.01	44.36 ± 0.03	110 ± 50	26.52 ± 0.02	30.55 ± 0.01	-	-1.55 ± 0.01	-0.1	0.7 ± 0.2
30	1	const*TBabs*(zpo + zga ^(l))	2.33 ^{+0.01} _{-0.02}	-	28 ± 1	23 ⁺³ ₋₂	44.14 ± 0.03	44.01 ± 0.04	50 ± 20	26.23 ± 0.02	-	30.58 ± 0.01	-	-	-
31	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.05 ± 0.06	120 ± 20	22.8 ± 0.5	21 ± 1	44.95 ± 0.01	44.88 ± 0.02	40 ± 20	27.06 ± 0.01	30.79 ± 0.01	-	-1.43 ± 0.01	-0.3	0.3 ± 0.1
32	1	const*TBabs*(zpo + zga ^(l))	2.04 ± 0.01	-	24.2 ± 0.2	29.1 ± 0.6	45.60 ± 0.01	45.64 ± 0.01	170 ± 80	27.76 ± 0.01	32.06 ± 0.01	30.82 ± 0.01	-1.65 ± 0.01	-0.1	-
33	1	const*TBabs*zpo	2.08 ± 0.04	-	9.2 ± 0.2	10.2 ± 0.6	45.26 ± 0.02	45.27 ± 0.01	200 ± 100	27.41 ± 0.01	-	32.09 ± 0.01	-	-	-
34	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.6 ± 0.2	230 ± 30	4.4 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	6.9 ^{+0.6} _{-0.9}	43.61 ± 0.02	44.72 ^{+0.03} _{-0.04}	3 ± 2	25.74 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	0.6 ± 0.5
35	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.4 ± 0.1	280 ⁺⁴ ₋₅	20.8 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	7.6 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	43.92 ± 0.01	43.33 ± 0.04	40 ± 20	25.58 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	1.4 ± 0.3
36	1	const*TBabs*zpo	1.84 ± 0.03	-	13.5 ^{+0.2} _{-0.3}	21.1 ± 0.9	46.03 ± 0.02	46.20 ± 0.01	80 ± 40	28.26 ± 0.01	32.13 ± 0.01	-	-1.49 ± 0.01	0.3	-
37	1	const*TBabs*(zga ^(l) + zbb + zbb ^(r) + zpo)	2.23 ^{+0.09} _{-0.11}	108 ⁺³ ₋₁₀	114.62 ^{+0.08} _{-0.42}	34 ± 1	44.02 ± 0.01	43.40 ± 0.01	70 ± 30	25.62 ± 0.01	29.41 ± 0.01	32.16 ± 0.01	-1.45 ± 0.01	-0.1	2.1 ± 0.3
38	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.39 ± 0.08	110 ± 10	16.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	10.4 ± 0.9	44.63 ± 0.01	44.25 ± 0.02	160 ± 80	26.49 ^{+0.01} _{-0.02}	30.62 ± 0.01	29.48 ± 0.02	-1.59 ± 0.01	-0.1	0.5 ± 0.1
39	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.45 ± 0.09	136 ± 6	57 ± 1	25 ± 2	43.83 ± 0.01	43.42 ± 0.03	50 ± 30	25.68 ± 0.02	29.34 ± 0.01	30.65 ± 0.01	-1.40 ± 0.01	-0.4	0.5 ± 0.1
40	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.3 ± 0.1	134 ± 4	11.8 ± 0.3	5.3 ± 0.6	44.81 ± 0.01	44.13 ± 0.03	200 ± 100	26.35 ± 0.02	30.58 ± 0.01	29.37 ± 0.01	-1.62 ± 0.01	-0.3	2.6 ± 0.5
41	1	const*TBabs*zpo	2.09 ± 0.02	-	38.3 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4}	40 ± 1	45.36 ± 0.01	45.37 ± 0.01	30 ± 10	27.50 ± 0.01	-	30.60 ± 0.01	-	-	-
42	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.9 ± 0.1	200 ± 50	4.9 ^{+0.1} _{-0.4}	6.6 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	45.04 ^{+0.09} _{-0.06}	44.99 ± 0.02	70 ± 30	27.08 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	0.6 ± 0.3
43	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.7 ± 0.1	122 ± 6	6.9 ± 0.2	7.4 ± 0.8	43.82 ± 0.01	43.59 ^{+0.03} _{-0.04}	500 ± 200	25.57 ± 0.03	30.54 ± 0.01	-	-1.33 ± 0.01	-0.2	2.4 ± 0.4
44	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.2 ± 0.1	150 ± 10	4.9 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	3.2 ± 0.2	44.31 ± 0.02	44.89 ± 0.03	6 ± 3	26.09 ± 0.03	-	30.59 ± 0.01	-	-	1.2 ± 0.4
45	1	const*TBabs*zpo	2.03 ± 0.06	-	14.0 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	17 ± 1	44.91 ± 0.03	44.95 ± 0.02	110 ± 50	27.07 ± 0.02	-	-	-	-	-
46	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.2 ± 0.1	160 ± 20	18.8 ± 0.6	13 ± 1	43.75 ± 0.01	43.50 ± 0.04	50 ± 20	25.69 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-	0.5 ± 0.4
47	1	const*TBabs*zpo	1.94 ± 0.03	-	6.7 ± 0.1	8.7 ± 0.4	45.04 ± 0.02	45.14 ± 0.01	60 ± 30	27.23 ± 0.01	31.10 ± 0.02	-	-1.49 ± 0.01	-0.4	-
48	1	const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	2.0 ± 0.1	160 ⁺³⁰ ₋₃₀	10.4 ± 0.3	11.3 ± 0.9	44.58 ^{+0.03} _{-0.02}	44.48 ± 0.02	140 ± 70	26.60 ^{+0.03} _{-0.02}	30.73 ± 0.02	31.13 ± 0.02	-1.59 ± 0.01	-0.2	0.5 ± 0.2

Continuation of Table C.1

ID # (1) (2)	Model (3)	W-stat/dof (dof) (4)	Γ (5)	kT_{bb} (6)	$F_{0.5-2\text{keV}}$ (7)	$F_{2-10\text{keV}}$ (8)	$\log L_{0.5-2\text{keV}}$ (9)	$\log L_{2-10\text{keV}}$ (10)	$k_{\text{bol,X}}$ (11)	$\log L_{2\text{keV}}$ (12)	$\log L_{2500\text{\AA}}$ (13)	$\log L_{4400\text{\AA}}$ (14)	α_{ox} (15)	$\log A_{\text{Edd,O/UV}}$ (16)	$R_{\text{S}/P}$ (17)
49	1 const*TBabs*zpo	0.98 (105)	1.76 ± 0.05	—	11.9 ± 0.4	20 ± 2	44.89 ± 0.03	45.11 ± 0.02	300 ± 200	27.13 ± 0.02	31.98 ± 0.01	30.75 ± 0.02	-1.86 ± 0.01	-0.2	—
50	1 const*TBabs*zpo	0.90 (80)	1.82 ± 0.05	—	5.0 ^{+0.1} _{-0.2}	7.8 ± 0.6	44.96 ± 0.03	45.14 ± 0.02	50 ± 30	27.19 ± 0.02	—	32.01 ± 0.01	—	—	—
51	1 const*TBabs*zpo	1.04 (240)	2.11 ± 0.02	—	24.9 ± 0.3	25.3 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	45.94 ± 0.01	45.94 ± 0.01	160 ± 70	28.08 ± 0.01	32.55 ± 0.01	—	-1.72 ± 0.01	0.2	—
52	1 const*TBabs*zpo	0.96 (167)	2.04 ± 0.04	—	7.2 ± 0.2	8.2 ± 0.5	44.30 ± 0.02	45.34 ± 0.01	190 ± 90	27.46 ± 0.01	31.51 ± 0.02	32.58 ± 0.01	-1.55 ± 0.01	-0.5	—
53	1 const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.98 (295)	2.01 ± 0.05	122 ± 3	46.5 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	39 ± 2	44.83 ± 0.01	44.54 ± 0.01	160 ± 70	26.65 ± 0.01	31.13 ± 0.01	31.54 ± 0.02	-1.72 ± 0.01	0.1	1.2 ± 0.1
54	1 const*TBabs*zTBabs ^(a) *zpo	0.95 (114)	1.7 ± 0.1	—	1.68 ^{+0.05} _{-0.02}	4.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	45.1 ± 0.1	45.39 ± 0.03	800 ± 400	27.38 ± 0.07	—	31.15 ± 0.01	—	—	—
55	1 const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.02 (54)	2.4 ± 0.2	140 ± 20	10.2 ^{+0.2} _{-0.3}	5.7 ± 0.9	44.36 ± 0.02	43.98 ± 0.04	60 ± 30	26.23 ± 0.03	—	—	—	—	0.5 ± 0.2
56	1 const*TBabs*zedge ^(a) *zpo	1.04 (160)	1.78 ± 0.03	—	9.8 ± 0.2	13.5 ± 0.6	45.16 ± 0.02	45.36 ± 0.01	110 ± 50	27.39 ± 0.01	31.90 ± 0.01	—	-1.73 ± 0.01	0.0	—
57	1 const*TBabs*zpo	1.03 (78)	2.45 ± 0.05	—	3.7 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.2	44.90 ± 0.02	44.67 ± 0.02	80 ± 40	26.93 ± 0.01	30.82 ± 0.04	31.93 ± 0.01	-1.49 ± 0.02	-0.4	—
58	1 const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.00 (368)	1.76 ± 0.02	360 ⁺²⁰ ₋₃₀	28.3 ± 0.2	44.8 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	45.77 ± 0.01	45.93 ± 0.01	70 ± 30	28.01 ± 0.01	32.19 ± 0.01	30.85 ± 0.04	-1.60 ± 0.01	0.0	0.18 ± 0.04
59	1 const*TBabs*zpo	0.96 (90)	1.8 ± 0.1	—	1.7 ± 0.1	2.7 ± 0.4	44.46 ± 0.07	44.63 ± 0.03	70 ± 30	26.68 ± 0.04	—	32.22 ± 0.01	—	—	—
60	1 const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	1.02 (146)	2.00 ± 0.07	190 ⁺³⁰ ₋₄₀	13.0 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	14.4 ^{+0.9} _{-1.1}	45.40 ^{+0.05} _{-0.03}	45.29 ± 0.01	200 ± 100	27.42 ± 0.02	31.92 ± 0.01	—	-1.73 ± 0.01	-0.3	0.5 ± 0.2
61	1 const*TBabs*(zbb + zpo)	0.96 (202)	2.28 ^{+0.04} _{-0.05}	110 ± 10	65.1 ^{+0.9} _{-1.0}	50 ± 2	44.50 ± 0.01	44.28 ± 0.01	80 ± 30	26.48 ± 0.01	30.58 ± 0.01	31.95 ± 0.01	-1.57 ± 0.01	0.1	0.26 ± 0.05

Notes: (1) Unique X-HESS identifier; (2) Obs. Number; (3) best-fit model; (4) ratio between the W-stat value of the spectral fit and the degrees of freedom; (5) photon index; (6) blackbody temperature (eV); (7) absorbed $E = 0.5 - 2$ keV flux in units of 10^{-14} erg cm^{-2} s^{-1} ; (8) absorbed $E = 2 - 10$ keV flux in units of 10^{-14} erg cm^{-2} s^{-1} ; (9) intrinsic luminosity in the $E = 0.5 - 2$ keV band; (10) intrinsic luminosity in the $E = 2 - 10$ keV band; (11) X-ray bolometric correction calculated from L_{bol} in Rakshit et al. (2020) and the hard X-ray luminosity in column (10); (12) 2 keV rest-frame luminosity (erg s^{-1} Hz^{-1}); (13) 2500 $\text{\AA}$ rest-frame luminosity (erg s^{-1} Hz^{-1}); (14) 4400 $\text{\AA}$ rest-frame luminosity (erg s^{-1} Hz^{-1}); (15) α_{ox} parameter; (16) Eddington ratio from the simultaneous optical/UV OM data and Duran et al. (2020) optical bolometric correction (typical uncertainty of ~ 0.3 dex); (17) $R_{\text{S}/P}$ parameter, a proxy of the relative strength between the luminosity of the blackbody and power-law components in the $E = 0.5 - 2$ keV energy band. ^(a) The column density of the cold gas cloud is $N_{\text{H}} = (3 \pm 1) \times 10^{21}$ cm^{-2} ; ^(b) Photoelectric absorption by a gas cloud with $N_{\text{H}} = (3 \pm 2) \times 10^{21}$ cm^{-2} ; ^(c) The column density of the cold gas cloud is $N_{\text{H}} = (2 \pm 1) \times 10^{21}$ cm^{-2} ; ^(d) The column density of the cold gas cloud is $N_{\text{H}} = (3 \pm 1) \times 10^{21}$ cm^{-2} ; ^(e) Photoelectric absorption by a gas cloud with $N_{\text{H}} = 1.3^{+0.8}_{-0.7} \times 10^{22}$ cm^{-2} ; ^(f) Gaussian emission line at $E = 6.88^{+0.06}_{-0.03}$ keV, with unconstrained width and equivalent width of $EW = 160 \pm 50$ eV; ^(g) Additional blackbody component with $kT = 260 \pm 40$ eV; ^(h) Gaussian emission line at $E = 6.88 \pm 0.02$, with unconstrained width and an equivalent width of $EW = 200 \pm 40$ eV; ⁽ⁱ⁾ Gaussian emission line at $E = 6.54 \pm 0.06$, with unconstrained width and an equivalent width of $EW = 340 \pm 110$ eV; ^(j) Gaussian absorption line at $E = 1.01^{+0.04}_{-0.07}$ keV, with a width of $\sigma = 140^{+40}_{-20}$ eV and an equivalent width of FWHM = -90^{+30}_{-10} eV; ^(k) Ionised gas cloud with $N_{\text{H}} (10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}) = 36 \pm 8$, $\log \xi = 3.15^{+0.07}_{-0.05}$ erg cm^{-1} s^{-1} and fixed covering factor $C_{\text{r}} = 1$; ^(l) Gaussian absorption line at $E = 1.06^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$ keV, with a width of $\sigma = 120^{+40}_{-30}$ eV and an equivalent width of FWHM = -80 ± 10 eV; ^(m) Gaussian emission line at $E = 6.49^{+0.08}_{-0.07}$ keV, with a fixed width of $\sigma = 200$ eV and equivalent width of $EW = 190 \pm 60$ eV; ⁽ⁿ⁾ Additional blackbody component with $kT_{\text{bb}} = 80 \pm 3$ eV; ^(o) Gaussian emission line with fixed width $\sigma = 100$ eV at $E = 6.65^{+0.05}_{-0.04}$ keV, with an equivalent width of $EW = 100 \pm 20$ eV; ^(p) Gaussian absorption line at $E = 7.48 \pm 0.04$ keV, with a width of $\sigma = 260^{+50}_{-40}$ eV and an equivalent width of $EW = -340 \pm 40$ eV; ^(q) Gaussian emission line at $E = 3.80^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$ keV, with unresolved width and an equivalent width of $EW = 270 \pm 90$ eV; ^(r) Gaussian absorption line at $E = 1.10 \pm 0.01$ keV, with an unresolved width and an equivalent width of $EW = -70^{+20}_{-10}$ eV; ^(s) Gaussian emission line at $E = 6.58^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$ with an unresolved width and an equivalent width of $EW = 60 \pm 20$ eV; ^(t) Gaussian emission line at $E = 0.94^{+0.02}_{-0.03}$ eV, with a width of $\sigma = 100 \pm 20$ eV and an equivalent width of $EW = 50 \pm 20$ eV; ^(u) Additional blackbody component with $kT_{\text{bb}} = 200^{+40}_{-50}$ eV; ^(v) Cold absorbing gas cloud with column density of $N_{\text{H}} (10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}) = 5.6^{+1.6}_{-1.5}$; ^(w) Absorption edge at $E = 9.3 \pm 0.2$ keV and depth $\tau = 1.1 \pm 0.2$.

Fig. C.1: *XMM-Newton* spectra of the X-HESS AGN. Data from EPIC-pn, MOS1 and MOS2 are shown in black, red and blue, respectively. Data were divided by the response effective area for each particular channel. Best-fit model (solid green line) is shown for EPIC-pn only, for the sake of visual clarity. The bottom panel in each plot describes the ratio between the data and best-fit model. Spectra were rebinned with custom schemes for plotting purposes only.

Continuation of Fig. C.1.

Continuation of Fig. C.1.